

detected; in clay, it was calculated as 0.93 eggs mL⁻¹ soil. No differences in plant height between treatments in clay soil were observed at 84 DAS, although differences were observed at earlier growth stages. The root systems of infected plants were blackened, necrotic, and appeared stubby. This impairs the function of roots, particularly under conditions of low water availability.

H. sacchari is clearly highly pathogenic on susceptible upland rice in sandy soil. Very low initial population densities resulted in severe grain losses in sandy soil, whereas, in the heavier clay soil, rice was more tolerant of *H. sacchari*. The chlorosis, reduced vigor, and root damage observed in *H. sacchari*-infected plants are likely to further predispose crops to

existing stresses, such as weed competition and drought, exacerbating overall losses. *H. sacchari* egg Pi fitted the critical point model well, despite the presence of multiple nematode generations over the duration of the crop cycle. The good fit of *H. sacchari* to the model is attributed to the aggressiveness of the parasite early in the plant's growth. Field population densities similar to those used in the study likely occur in the field (Coyne et al 1996); moreover, conditions are representative of seedbed conditions. *H. sacchari* is therefore a potentially important threat to the sustainability of intensive upland rice production in West Africa, particularly with improved cultivars on sandy soils.

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Effect of *Heterodera sacchari* Pi cyst density on development of rice cv IDSA6 in sand and clay loam soil.*

Cyst density (L soil)	Sandy soil					Clay soil				
	GY	RFW	LDW	HT	RLCC	GY	RFW	LDW	HT	RLCC
0	3.5	19.1	7.5	904	33.2	6.4	9.4	9.7	960	28.8
1.25	1.6	12.3	10.3	889	31.1	6.9	10.7	10.9	985	28.6
2.5	2.8	9.7	7.3	918	30.8	6.5	8.5	8.1	879	28.1
6.25	1.7	8.2	6.3	667	22.2	4.9	9.2	8.7	947	28.4
12.5	1.8	5.8	7.8	707	31.6	5.2	9.0	8.7	916	30.3
25	1.2	5.2	5.8	642	33.1	5.3	8.7	7.4	899	28.5
50	0.9	2.9	5.2	429	15.0	3.5	5.5	5.1	754	26.1
LSD										
<0.05	1.63	6.8	ns	257	10.1	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
<0.01	ns	9.0	-	342	13.4	-	-	-	-	-
Interaction ^b	***	ns	ns	***	ns					

*GY = grain yield (g), RFW = root fresh weight (g), LDW = leaf dry weight (g), HT = plant height (mm) at 84 DAS, RLCC = relative leaf chlorophyll content at 84 DAS. LSD = least significant difference. ^bInteraction *H. sacchari* inoculum density × soil type. ***Significantly different at P<0.001, ns = not significant at P<0.05.

Relationship between relative yield of rice cv. IDSA6 and *Heterodera sacchari* Pi egg density in sandy and clay loam soils.

A simple method for evaluating the virulence of the brown planthopper

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To effectively use rice varieties resistant to the brown planthopper [BPH, *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål)], it is necessary to monitor the virulence of BPH populations. BPH virulence is controlled

polygenically. This character, however, does not exhibit a continuous distribution of phenotype but is a threshold character that has two distinct phenotypes—virulent and avirulent (Tanaka 1999).

Hence, a proportion of virulent individuals in a BPH population indicates a degree of virulence. For virulence tests of BPH individuals, many researchers have measured honeydew excretion of BPH

females using the parafilm-sachet method (Pathak et al 1982). This method is quantitative but very laborious and is not necessary if a study intends only to classify individuals as either virulent or avirulent. This paper describes a simple and easy method for evaluating the virulence of individual BPH.

The abdomina of virulent BPH females become swollen on a rice variety within a few days, whereas the abdomina of avirulent females remain thin or become thinner (Tanaka 1999). An experiment was conducted to demonstrate the usefulness of this character in classifying virulent and avirulent BPH. Three seeds of rice were sown in a 220-mL plastic cup. At the tillering stage (4-7 wk after sowing, varies due to season), all plant parts including tillers and leaf blades, were cut off leaving a 15-cm-long main stem (3 stems in a cup). Trimming the plants is not required although it made observation of insects easy and it minimized space requirements. Trimmed plants were covered with a transparent plastic cylindrical cage (5.5 cm diam × 20 cm height). Ten newly emerged brachypterous BPH females with thin abdomina were released into the cage, and the open end of the cage was covered with gauze. Test plants were kept in a laboratory controlled at 25 °C, 16 L (light):8 D (dark), and the BPH were observed every day. Swollen females were counted and removed from the cage. Females that became swollen or that survived for 5 d. were considered as virulent.

Four experiments were conducted with three BPH populations (see figure). One hundred females were tested per experiment. Test insects were classified

into four categories (dead, thin, medium, and swollen). Medium is the category wherein females appeared to be the least swollen. Most females either became swollen or died after 5 d. Thus, it was reasonable to end the tests at day 5. The proportion of females with swollen or medium abdomina at day 2 was almost the same as that of females that survived for 5 d. Thus, tests can be ended at day 2. To end the tests at day 2, however, it is necessary to discriminate between medium and thin abdomina. The difference between medium and thin abdomina will vary between observers. Thus, at 25 °C, it is best to continue the

tests until day 5. When tests are conducted at another temperature, the test period should be determined according to preliminary experiments because temperature affects the growth and development of BPH.

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Changes in number of females in four virulence categories. A: an ASD7-selected BPH strain on ASD7 (carrying *bph2*), B: a Mudgo-selected strain on Mudgo (*Bph1*), C: a strain (collected in Isahaya, Japan, in 1997) on Mudgo, D: the Isahaya-1997 strain on Babawee (*bph4*).

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